

Pesticide Impacts on Humans and Wildlife: A Systematic Synthesis of the Evidence

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SUMMARY

Pesticides are chemicals that are being used to control pests such as weeds, pathogens that affect plants, and other species. These are used in over 1,500 different ways around the world. They also provide a covert threat to everyone's ecosystems, including those of people, animals, and insects. They harm our lives, deteriorate our health, and wipe off helpful environmental organisms. People absorb these harmful substances via the water, food, agricultural goods, and environment. All pesticides should be employed carefully, and new pesticides need to be created that don't adversely hurt the ecosystem. Organophosphates are in the category of insecticides that alter the nervous system by disrupting the enzymes that adjust neurotransmitters. Carbamates also have the same function as such organophosphate, but their actions are sometimes reversible in nature. Pesticides exert negative effects on the environment and the health of fauna and flora. The extra use of pesticides devastates biodiversity. The efficacy of soil is much higher without these chemicals. Pesticides no doubt destroy pests, but they also harm the quality of soil. The soil without pesticides has a higher water-retaining capacity, which is favorable for plant growth. It is concluded that the pesticides have both harmful and beneficial effects. These are helpful for the better growth of crops and provide a threat to humans by direct inhalation.

Keywords: Pesticide, Neurotransmitter, Carbonates, Inhalation, Biodiversity

Citation: Shafiq, H. R., H. Ahmed, S. Younis, K. Iqbal, A. saddiqa, A. Fatima, I. Nazar, N. Iqbal, and M. K. Ullah. 2023. Pesticide Impacts on Humans and Wildlife: A Systematic Synthesis of the Evidence. International Journal of Forest Sciences 3(2):53-56.

Received: April, 2023; **Accepted:** May, 2023

INTRODUCTION

In fact, pesticides are a diverse group of chemicals that are being used globally (Kalyabina *et al.*, 2021). The Environment Protection Agency (EPA) defines pesticides as a class of chemical compounds used to manage and deter the population of pests. Pesticides are also defined as substances that are applied to manage or eradicate noxious pests such as weeds, pathogens that affect plants, and other species. It was also employed to control other living things like nematodes, arthropods like

insects, and mammals, which ruin our sources of food and lead to a variety of health issues (Rani *et al.*, 2021).

USES OF PESTICIDES

Pesticides are used in over 1500 different ways around the world; each has a unique structure as well as nature and has the potential to cause significant harm issues with the health and environment. About two million metric tonnes of pesticides are employed in farm production each year (Lima *et al.*, 2016). Pesticides provide a covert threat to everyone's ecosystems, including those of people, animals, and insects. They avoid matrix diseases among humans, manage pests, and are crucial to crop growth, yet they also severely contaminate our environment. The land, water, atmosphere, plants, nutrition, and feed all contain these hazardous chemicals. As a result of the food supply chain, their remnants end up in individuals and other animals, as well as plants and products. They harm our lives, deteriorate our health, and wipe off helpful environmental organisms. This essay presents material that was discovered through research in academic journals, books, or other resources. People absorb these harmful substances via the water, food, agricultural goods, and environment (Hashimi *et al.*, 2020).

PESTICIDES AND DISEASES

They also result in death and the development of numerous illnesses, tumors, and mutations. These substances decimate honeybee colonies and reduce the number of pollinators. The extensive use of pesticides also severely suppresses wildlife, animals, and soil microorganisms. They harm soil microbes, pollinators, honeybees, people, animals, and humanity. The population of butterflies, honeybees, and some other beneficial creatures declines as pesticide use increases, which also has an effect on human health. If these living things become less abundant, a lack of food, a failing economy, as well as an increase in the need for food and feed will endanger our survival, and emerging crises like famine and diseases will undermine our prosperity. All pesticides should be employed carefully, and new pesticides need to be created that don't adversely hurt the ecosystem (Hashimi *et al.*, 2020; Faiz, 2022). Because all pesticides are hazardous agents, they must be tested and certified by the office of authority. The health of people and other non-target organisms may be affected by extra exposure routes, which can also affect ecological systems and the movement of polluted material by water and wind (Silva *et al.*, 2020).

DISCUSSION

Any substance that is used to eliminate pests or other organisms that are harmful for crops are known as pesticide. It is a substance that retards, disable, deform and destroy pests (Dreistadt, 2016). There are some major categories of pesticides, insecticides used to ruin insects, fungicides used to ruin fungi, herbicide used to ruin weeds and herbs and rodenticides used to ruin rodents. Some other kinds of pesticides are; bactericides are utilized to eradicate bacteria and larvicides are utilized to eradicate larvae. Some pesticides are supposed to be biodegradable that can be destitute by some microorganisms into substances that are harmless. Other pesticides are persistent that may take several months or even years to break. Organophosphates

are under the category of insecticides that alter the nervous system by disorder the enzymes that adjust neurotransmitters (Radhakrishnan *et al.*, 2017). Carbamates are also has same function as such organophosphate but its action sometimes are reversible in nature. At ancient time organochlorine is used as insecticide but later it is banned due to some hazardous effects. Certain pesticides are obtained from natural substances such as plants and animals are called biopesticides. The major worth of pesticides is that it can defend crop from pests (Nawaz *et al.*, 2016; Irshad and Hussain, 2023).

Pesticides exert negative effects on environment and health of fauna & flora (Faiz, 2022; Irshad and Hussain, 2023). The extra use of pesticides devastates biodiversity. The pesticide is a deadly substance or combination of distinct substances that are utilized to retard or eradicate the pests (Egbuna and Sawicka, 2019; Kala *et al.*, 2020). Pesticide efforts fulfil to drag insects, herbs, pathogens and pests. A pest is an organism that poses a threat to present a danger to our food and health. The utility of pesticide is augmented day by day over the past decades (Naranjo and Ellsworth, 2009). The utility of pesticide is not confined to only fields but also utilized at homes for domestic purposes. Pesticides are dangerous chemicals which are utilized to harm pathogens or pests. It is found in soil water, rain water and seeps down to underground water (Mishra, 2023). The water flows surrounding of agricultural crop.

The efficacy of soil is much higher without any these of chemicals. Pesticides no doubt destruct pests but it also harms negatively to quality of soil. The soil without pesticides has higher water retaining capacity that is favourable for plant growth. The animals intake the food which is contaminated with pesticides. The excessive use of pesticides in a particular area leads shortage of food sources (Alvarez *et al.*, 2017). This thing also affected food chains and disturbs whole ecosystem. Recent research revealed that many species of birds are died due to augmentation of chemicals in their pests. The vital component of pesticides, fungicides affects birds little bit but insecticides kill the species of birds. A small quantity of pesticide is enough to destruct a bird (Maurya *et al.*, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Using a lot of insecticides is ineffective and wastes money. Some insecticides help reduce pests, but they are harmful to our health and the environment, so they are not a long-term answer. Even natural pesticides can lose effectiveness when bugs develop resistance to them. As a result, the ideal answer is to employ something known as integrated pest management. Pesticides can harm both humans and animals. They can create health issues such as illnesses, diseases, allergies, and breathing difficulties. Pesticides can harm our pets as well. Pesticides, on the other hand, can assist keep humans healthy by destroying germs, pests, and hazardous plants. It's a good idea to start with non-chemical procedure. Some modern insecticides derived from nature are safer than older ones. Making food in a way that is healthier for the environment and people's health is a significant future challenge.

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